

IDIOPATHIC INFERTILITY MANAGEMENT WITH AYURVEDA – A CASE STUDY

Dr. Kamayani Mishra*

MD Dravyaguna (Ayurveda medical Officer Pt. Uddhavdas Mehta Govt. Ayurveda Hospital)
Bhopal Madhya Pradesh.

Article Received on 15 April 2026,
Article Revised on 05 May 2026,
Article Published on 16 May 2026,

<https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.20225143>

*Corresponding Author

Dr. Kamayani Mishra

MD Dravyaguna (Ayurveda medical
officer Pt. Uddhavdas Mehta Govt.
Ayurveda Hospital) Bhopal Madhya
Pradesh.

How to cite this Article: Dr. Kamayani Mishra*
(2026). Idiopathic Infertility Management With
Ayurveda – A Case Study. World Journal of
Pharmaceutical Research, 15(10), 1208–1212.

This work is licensed under Creative Commons
Attribution 4.0 International license.

ABSTRACT

In some cases the reason of infertility is unexplained in which all the reports are normal but still a female is unable to conceive after unprotected coitus for 12 months or more. Approximately 15 to 30 percent of couples face idiopathic infertility. In this case 26 year female came in *Ayurveda* opd with a complaint of unable to conceive and was very stressed as well as depressed as she has taken a lot of treatment before at other places. As there are always two sides of coin so if we see the positive aspect in this then we can say that people believe that when they get disappointment else then they see *Ayurveda* treatment as miracle to be happened.

KEYWORDS: *Ayurveda, idiopathic infertility, Stress treatment.*

INTRODUCTION

In *Ayurveda Acharya Charak* has primarily discussed about *Vandhya, Apraja, and Supraja* in context of reproductive health in *Shareer Sthan* and *Chikitsa sthan*.

Vandhya^[1] (absolute infertility) - it is considered as incurable due to congenital or any anatomical acquired causes.

Apraja vandhya^[2] (primary infertility) - it refers to a woman who has not conceived even once.

Supraja^[3] (secondary infertility) - where a woman is unable to conceive during her potential years after giving birth to one child.

Acharya Shushruta in Shareer Sthan defined about the four factors which are responsible for conception ritu which refers to ovulation period, *Kshetram* which refers to female reproductive system, *Ambu* which refers to nourishment and *Beej* which refers to sperm and ovum quality.^[4] In same context in *Shareer Sthan Acharya* says that *Shukra and Shonit* unites with *Atma, Astha prakrati, Shodasha vikar* in uterus is called *Garbha*.^[5]

So by the above description it is very clear that there is no any single factor is responsible for conception. Both the couple should be physically and mentally fit for conception. In this case study the patient came with lot of stress and depression. So a prescription was planned keeping the entire concept in mind. We all know that in all the female problems drug of choice is *Ashoka*, therefore the medicines which were selected all has *Ashoka* as a main ingredient.

CASE STUDY

A 26 year old patient came to OPD with a complaint of unable to conceive and with a problem of white discharge. She came with only ultrasound report and there was no abnormality in her report. There was no problem in ultrasound but still she was unable to conceive and was very depressed as she was taking treatment in other system of medicine since last 1 year. Her financial condition was also weak so she came with a hope in government *Ayurveda* hospital OPD. When a detailed history was taken then a problem of sperm leakage just after coitus came into notice. Her husband has not undergone with any investigation and was not willing to go with investigation or any test so to start medicines for her husband without any report was necessary as patient was in very pity condition and was helpless. So the treatment started without detail investigation. First counseling of patient was done to make her understand that she is normal to conceive. Medicines which were available in hospital were given and some important medicine which was required was given in patent form, keeping financial condition of patient in mind.

Treatment given to female patient

S.no	Name of medicine	Dose and duration
1	<i>Pradraghna churna</i>	3 gm bd with lukewarm water before meal for 15 days
2	<i>Pushyanug churna(60gm) with godanti bhasma(10gm)</i>	3 gm bd with rice water before meal for 10 days
3	<i>Jatyadi tail</i>	For 10 days <i>Pichu dharan</i>
4	<i>Yavani churna</i>	3 gm bd with lukewarm water daily after meal
5	Syrup amycordial forte	10 ml bd before meal for 30 days

6	Tab aloes compound	2 bd before meal for 30 days
7	Tab leptaden	2 bd before meal for 30 days

Treatment given to husband of patient

S.no	Name of medicine	Dose and duration
1	<i>Ashwagandha churna</i>	5 gm bd with milk for 30 days
2	Tab confido	1 bd for 30 days
3	Tab tentex forte	1 bd for 30 days

The above treatment was started the day she came to OPD. She and her husband was advised to continue the treatment till the date of periods of every month as prescribed and if time exceeds in month for date then discontinue the treatment and test for pregnancy. She gave follow up in every 15th day and her periods were missed in second month after starting treatment so a pregnancy test was done which turned out to be positive. After that for confirmation an ultrasound was performed in government hospital in which her pregnancy was confirmed.

DISCUSSION

In *Ayurveda* there is a deep and direct correlation between mental and physical state. It is bidirectional and biological infertility can be caused due to psychological distress and this condition of infertility itself triggers more mental stress and depression. This mental stress causes a reproductive failure due to unhealthy sperm and ovum. In *Ayurveda* a happy, peaceful state of mind between both the partners is required for successful conception. So in this case a major role was played by counseling. Patient was having a problem of white discharge so to rectify the local infection *Jatyadi tail Pichu* was advised as there are only OPD level facilities. To rectify the *Apan Vayu Vikriti* all the medicines were given before meal as medicine time for *Apan Vayu* is *Pragbhakt* in *Ayurveda*. Patient was having a problem of sperm leakage just after coitus therefore medicine to improve sperm motility and count was given to her husband.

Pushyanug churna:- It is a poly herb combination which is widely used during practice for numerous hormonal troubles. In *Ayurveda* one of its indications is *Garbhaprada* and is very good in regularizing levels of FSH and LH. So being a very significant uterine tonic it improves fertility by regular use. *Ashoka*, *Lodhra*, *Amla*, work together to promote reproductive health.^[6]

Pradraghna churna: *Pradraghna churna* is generally prescribed in condition like leucorrhoea, PCOS, uterine fibroids, hormonal imbalance. Key ingredients of *pradraghna churna* are *Ashoka*, *Lodhra*, and *Arjuna* which improves the health of reproductive tissues.^[7-8]

Amy cordial forte: its key ingredients are *Ashoka*, *Lodhra*, *Shatavar*, *Ashwagandha*, *Tagar*, *Nagkesar*, *Priyangu* etc. because of *Tagar* and *Ashwagandha* it also normalizes mental stress and disturbances by essential nutrients which support overall emotional health and promote a balanced, calm state of mind and promote overall balance in feminine health.^[9]

The chemical constituent Procyanidin B2, luteolin and ketosterolin present in *Ashoka*, reduce the high estrogen and androgen levels.^[10]

CONCLUSION

In the current situation of society it is very noticeable that the percentage of idiopathic infertility is increasing day by day because of deep mental stress in coping up with the world. Financial pressure along with family pressure increases the mental load which leads to a lot of physical problems. Under such circumstances people start treating reproduction as a part of work which leads to idiopathic infertility. A person needs to understand that to reproduce a healthy baby it's very important to lead a healthy life style and this is the main reason why *Ayurveda* plays a major and important role as it always focuses equally on mental health.

REFERENCES

1. *Charak samhita*, of *Agnivesa*, elaborated by *Charaka* and *Dridhabala*, Edited with *Charaka-Candrika* Hindi commentary along with special deliberation by Dr. *Brahmanand Tripathi*, second part *Shareer sthan* chapter 4 verse 30 *Chaukambha Surbharati Prakashan*, Varanasi, 3rd Edition, 1994; pg 779.
2. *Charak samhita*, of *Agnivesa*, elaborated by *Charaka* and *Dridhabala*, Edited with *Charaka-Candrika* Hindi commentary along with special deliberation by Dr. *Brahmanand Tripathi*, first part *Chikitsa sthan* chapter 30 verse 7-8 *Chaukambha Surbharati Prakashan*, Varanasi, 3rd Edition, 1994; pg 754.
3. *Charak samhita*, of *Agnivesa*, elaborated by *Charaka* and *Dridhabala*, Edited with *Charaka-Candrika* Hindi commentary along with special deliberation by Dr. *Brahmanand Tripathi*, second part *Shareer sthan* chapter 8 verse 3 *Chaukambha Surbharati Prakashan*, Varanasi, 3rd Edition, 1994; pg 813.

4. *Sushruta samhita*,. *Susrutvimarshni* Hindi commentary by *Anantaram Sharma* Varanasi 2004 *Sharir Sthana*, chapter 2 verse 33 *Subharati Prakashana*, pg. no. 25-28.
5. *Sushruta samhita*,. *Susrutvimarshni* Hindi commentary by *Anantaram Sharma* Varanasi 2004 *Sharir Sthana*, chapter 5 verse 3 *Subharati Prakashana*, pg. no. 488.
6. Dr.Punam kumara, Dr Vinod kumar, Dr Pooja Sharma and Dr Anupam pathak, study the role of *Pushyanug churna* in management of *Pradar Wjpmr*, 2019; 5(9): 100-102.
7. <https://www.eayur.com> surfed on 7.5.2026 at 11am.
8. <https://www.myupchar.com> surfed on 7.05.2026 at 11:30 am.
9. <https://aimilpharmaceuticals.com> surfed on 7.05.2026 at 11.45 am.
10. <https://japsonline.com> surfed on 7.05.2026 at 12 pm.
11. <https://en.wikipedia.org/wiki/infertility> surfed on 06.05.2026 at 9 pm.